

WHEN CULTURE AND ART DO NOT PROGRESS, SOCIETY DOES NOT DEVELOP

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Abstract: In this article, the implementation of new historical fundamental reforms in the fields of culture and art, as in all spheres of life of the people of Uzbekistan, was widely established. Problems accumulated in the field, namely, the management of the culture and art sphere, the formation of a qualified personnel training system and the development of its mechanisms, the strengthening of the material and technical base of educational institutions and professional theaters and other institutions of the industry in the field of culture and art, the social protection of artists and Art Workers of theater-concert organizations it has been mentioned that issues such as further improvement of the system are the most important tasks in the development of our national culture and art.

Key words: culture, art, development, society, initiative, field, project, creativity, decree, faror, document, leader, fruit, scientist, generation, spirituality, theater.

КОГДА КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО НЕ ПРОГРЕССИВАЮТ, ОБЩЕСТВО НЕ РАЗВИВАЕТСЯ.

Аннотация: В данной статье широко установлено проведение новых исторических фундаментальных реформ в области культуры и искусства, как и во всех сферах жизни народа Узбекистана. Проблемы, накопившиеся в сфере, а именно: управление сферой культуры и искусства, формирование системы подготовки квалифицированных кадров и развитие ее механизмов, укрепление материально-технической базы учебных заведений и профессиональных театров и других учреждений промышленности в сфере культуры и искусства, социальной защиты деятелей искусств и деятелей искусств театрально-концертных организаций отмечено, что такие вопросы, как дальнейшее

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF 2024 = 5.073/Volume-2, Issue-6

совершенствование системы, являются важнейшими задачами в развитии нашей национальной культуры и искусства. .

Ключевые слова: культура, искусство, развитие, общество, инициатива, сфера, проект, творчество, указ, фарор, документ, лидер, плод, учёный, поколение, духовность, театр.

At the initiative of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in our country, promising projects that are being implemented in all areas, large-scale creative work carried out in places, are radically changing not only the lifestyle of our people, but also the worldview. Such a noble process can also be seen in the example of high attention paid to the development of culture and art, to the people of creativity. In the last two years, about 20 decrees and decisions related to this area have been adopted and efforts are being made on their implementation. The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 28, 2018” on approval of the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan " is of particular importance as an important document aimed at eliminating existing problems and shortcomings on this front. Consequently, in the words of the head of our state, society will not develop if culture and art do not progress in our country. In addition, there are many historical examples of the fact that the true effect of progress is measured not by the level of wealth or strength, but by how high the national culture has risen. For example, Philipson Martin, an English art scholar, writes that “rulers who, like the Temurians, appreciate their art and culture have never been to Central Asia”. In this sense, the initiative of the head of our state to develop the concept of further development of national culture also covers the fundamental roots of our thinking, our attitude to life, our work to create the present, the next, the spiritual maturity of the nation and the people, the enlightened future of our people, " we will not be mistaken. The concept consists of five chapters. It sets out a number of priorities that should be implemented in the future. In particular, it is envisaged to regulate relations in the field of Culture, establish the legal status of institutions in the system, create a legal base of social protection of creators, a system of training and training of personnel, and expand the material technical capabilities of cultural and art institutions. A number of measures have also been established, such as the full implementation of information and communication technologies in the field, the participation of real talent in international

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF 2024 = 5.073/Volume-2, Issue-6

festivals and competitions, the establishment of creative cooperation with foreign organizations in the field.

Of course, all this represents how much the concept of further development of our national culture plays in the cultural life of our country. After all, it will also be a guideline in overcoming serious problems that have accumulated in the industry. There is no doubt that such a modern method of cultural service will give its positive result in the full satisfaction of the spiritual needs of our people. Because autoclubs are not limited to concert-performance activities, they carry out the delivery of books, newspapers and magazines to the inhabitants of remote regions, organize dialogues with famous writers, poets, theater figures, political commentators, organize creative evenings. Another issue: 252 of the 894 former culture and population recreation centers that have existed in our country so far have been renovated and operating in NOM. In the remaining 642, repairs were nearly halted. The issues of providing musical instruments, sound amplification tools and other necessary equipment are also in a deplorable state. The solution to these important and very pressing issues is also expressed in the decision.

It is impossible to reach the end of our country by counting the incomparable opportunities created in order to raise the culture of our people, to make art more prosperous. It is permissible for us to perceive these sincerely and persistently. Already for centuries, it is worth taking every pride in such instructive works as tatigulik. And what is required of us is selfless work for the further prosperity of our national culture. Because the people of national culture exalted will have a strong position in the world community. As in all spheres of life of the people of Uzbekistan, the implementation of new historical fundamental reforms in the areas of culture and art was widely established. Problems accumulated in the field, namely, the management of the culture and art sphere, the formation of a qualified personnel training system and the development of its mechanisms, the strengthening of the material and technical base of educational institutions and professional theaters and other institutions of the industry in the field of culture and art, the social protection of artists and Art Workers of theater-concert organizations issues such as further improvement of the system were among the most important tasks in the development of our national culture and art."It is known that the culture and art of each nation is its pride and pride. Today, all our work on the development of our national culture and art is aimed at this goal. We should never forget

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one fact, society will not develop in our country if culture and art do not progress,” President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said at a meeting with the heads of the Ministry of Culture on December 25, 2017: “we should never forget one fact: society will not develop if culture and art do not progress in our country. The level of development of our people is first assessed according to our national culture. In this sense, culture is the image of our people, society. As long as we have begun to create a new image of Uzbekistan, we must first start with the development of our national culture.

The era itself shows that at a time when the relationship of today's market economy is developing, special attention should be paid to modern sciences associated with the development of the fields of culture and art. In particular, there is a great need for disciplines such as management problems, management culture, the basics of managing the art and cultural sphere. Management culture, along with being a component of human culture, also has a number of distinctive features. Therefore, first of all, the administrator himself must be civilized. Taking into account the specifics of the fields of culture and art, the organization of the Center for retraining and training of pedagogical personnel and their professional development is also of great importance at the Institute for retraining pedagogical personnel involved in the field at the Republican level. President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev signed a resolution “on measures to further develop and improve the activities of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan” aimed at developing the activities of another large scientific institution in the field of culture and art. The main goal of the decision is to comprehensively develop the art of music, which is of paramount importance and importance in raising the worldview, spiritual level and aesthetic education of our people, in particular, young people, to deeply study our rich musical heritage, to educate the younger generation in the spirit of love for classical samples of national and World musical it was determined to consist of further improvement.

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